

STRUCTURE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSON PLAN

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Abstract. *Lesson planning is one of integral aspects of teaching English overseas, however it's likewise one of the most time-consuming and tedious. Many plans even involve certainly what the instructor should say during a class, and the anticipated response from students. This article discusses the peculiarities of lesson planning on English language.*

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Introduction. In the last few years, learning a foreign language has become not a way of self-development, but a necessity. A foreign language has become a mandatory component of education not only in schools and universities, but also in many preschool educational institutions.

It would be useful to start the article by defining the keywords that will be used hereafter. Rudimentary, I would like to begin with the definition of **Language education**, according to (Wikipedia, 2020) language education is the process and practice of teaching a language as a second or foreign one. It is a branch of applied linguistics but can be an interdisciplinary field. Many methods could be used in Language education started from simple and straightforward ones until you can reach the most complicated and developed ones.

Technology according to the Cambridge Dictionary, technology is knowledge, equipment, and methods that are used in science and industry. When we start discussing technology most probably the first thing that came to our minds is computer-based technology. However, it is not fair to consider computer-based technologies as the only or the main method used as a technological means in a classroom space. (Chun et al., 2016).

While **Educational materials** could be defined as any visual and auditory pieces, textbooks, and items that enhance student understanding of the subject matter. Research on using technology in education has been increased recently so the purpose of this article is to review the historical development of technology use and put together the key findings on two levels. The first is on the classroom level where the education is taking place in a face-to-face approach and on a virtual level where education is provided remotely where the dependency on technology is much higher not only as an assisting tool but also as a mediating tool to provide education. I will try also to explain the advantages and disadvantages of using technology for educational purposes. Many tools have been used such as computers, robots, mobile phones, social networking, etc. for language education. These tools have been injected with developing operating systems like artificial intelligence and other innovations to make them more accessible and interactive (Crompton et al., 2020).

Lesson planning is one of integral aspects of teaching English overseas, however it's likewise one of the most time-consuming and tedious. Many plans even involve certainly what the instructor should say during a class, and the anticipated response from students. When this may be crucial at times, the more profitable you get in the classroom, the less of a structured plan you will need to support.

The details and elements of lesson plans are varied in accordance with the specific format mandated by a school, lyceum and college.

Notwithstanding, the common components of a good lesson plan include the following items:

- 1) Lesson's Theme.
- 2) The period of time (in minutes, hours, days, or weeks) necessary to complete the lesson.
- 3) Class details (class name or section, age, skill level, etc.)
- 4) The lesson objectives.
- 5) Instructional approach(es) to be used (this section describes the sequence of learning events as well as the techniques the teacher will use in helping students achieve the lesson objectives).
- 6) Instructional materials (such as a film, an image gallery, a music video, etc.).
- 7) Summary of and derived conclusions from the lesson.
- 8) Methods for practicing the lesson concepts.
- 9) Evaluation and testing methods to be used.
- 10) Contingency plans or elements (This section describes subsidiary topics or additional techniques and materials that can be used to either fortify the learning gains generated during the session or productively fill up excess time. Fun and engaging, seat work, dialogues, and other activities are ideal for this section).

Unless a specific lesson plan format is required by the learning type of institution, most English language practitioners tailor their lesson plans according to the teaching philosophies or techniques they believe in or are most comfortable with. In general, however, excellent English language lesson plans have common characteristics that a teacher should integrate in his/her own teaching strategies:

- a. Ideal lesson plans have a concise summary that fits on a single page. The detailed plan proper may - and often - exceeds this number, but the idea is to allow anyone to have a quick overview of the lesson.
- b. Great lesson plans are organized in a way that is easy and a delight to follow.
- c. Lesson plans should be strongly aligned with the needs and learning competencies of their intended audience.
- d. Each individual lesson plan should adhere to a continuity of lesson concepts and should not only fit in the curriculum but also reflect the overall vision of the subject.
- e. English language Lesson plans should establish platforms for learners to apply language learning to real-world situations.

In English language education lesson plans are crucial even in purely conversational classes. In order to establish an environment that encourages high quality learning and draws non-native speakers to articulate themselves extensively, adequate preparation is of paramount importance. Having a haphazardly designed plan is also inexcusable.

The most important for teachers is to define aims and objectives of a lesson. At the beginning of the lesson planning a teacher should answer the following questions:

- 1) What language and speech material will students learn within this lesson?
- 2) What do they know and are able or unable to do before the beginning of the lesson and what results they are able to achieve at the end of the lesson?

Answering the first question a teacher formulates the aim of the lesson, whereas the answer

to the second question gives a teacher the objectives.

Then a teacher should answer the following questions:

1. What kind of language-learning opportunities does the lesson provide?
2. How many opportunities are there for learners to practice meaningful use of the language?
3. Who has most of the opportunities for language use during the lesson - the teacher or the students?
4. Do all of the students participate in the lesson, or will some students have more opportunities for participation and practice than others?

The structure of a lesson is determined by how a teacher deals with three essential stages of a lesson: opening, sequencing, and closing.

Opening. This phase of the lesson serves primarily to focus the learners' attention on the aims of the lesson, to make links to previous learning, to arouse interest in the lesson, to activate background knowledge, or to preview language or strategies learners may need to understand in order to complete activities at the lesson.

Sequencing. A lesson is normally devoted to more than one type of activity, and teachers often have a «script» or preferred sequence that they follow when teaching a particular type of a lesson (speaking, listening, reading or writing lessons). A common lesson sequence found in many traditional language classes *consists* of a sequence of activities referred to as PPP and other approaches.

In communicative language teaching lessons often begin with *accuracy-based activities* and move toward *fluency-based activities*.

Reading lessons often follow a format consisting of *Pre-reading*, *While-reading*, and *Post-reading* activities.

Listening lessons follow a similar format. Conversation lessons often begin with controlled practice activities, such as dialogue practice, and move toward open-ended activities, such as role plays. Lessons based on a task-based approach often follow a sequence consisting of *Pre-task activities*, a *task cycle*, the *language focus*, and a *Follow-up task*.

The lesson sequence depends on principles such as «easier before more difficult activities» «receptive before productive skills» or «accuracy activities before fluency activities» Planning a lesson a teacher should handle the transitions between the different sequences of the lesson.

Closing. The closing phase of a lesson is also an significant part of a lesson sequence. Ideally, it should leave the students with a feeling that they have successfully achieved the target they set for themselves or that had been established for the lesson, and that the lesson was worthwhile and meaningful.

At the end of a lesson, it is usually valuable to summarize what the lesson has tried to achieve, to reinforce the points of the lesson, to suggest a follow-up work as appropriate, and to prepare students for what will follow. It is always important to praise the students for their effort and performance. During the closing stage, students may raise issues or problems that they would like to discuss or resolve; at this time, a teacher may also encourage them to ask him/her for suggestions concerning how they can improve.

Planning for transitions involves thinking about how the momentum of the lesson will be maintained during a transition - for example, while moving from a whole-class activity to a group-work activity; another issue that teachers need to consider is what students should do between

transitions - for example, if some students complete an activity before the others.

Teachers generally enjoy their time in the classroom, and teaching from one perspective is a kind of performance. However, according to R. Senior it is important to remember that «performing» is not the key goal of teaching. Facilitating students' performance is a more important goal.

One way of increasing the amount of students' participation during a lesson is to vary the grouping arrangements that a teacher uses; in this way, the teacher does not always dominate the lesson. The use of pair work and group work is one method that has been shown to ensure that students participate actively at a lesson.

By way of conclusion, at the end of the article, it is worth mentioning that for each lesson, the instructor must make a plan as a lesson development before starting the lesson. This is definitely a sign that the teacher is responsible. At the same time, it increases the effectiveness of the lesson.

REFERENCES

1. 10 PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN SCHOOLS
2. Tolipova Zebuniso Ulugbekovna
3. Z.Tolipova. Педагогический подход учителя к проведению урока.
4. Makhkamova G.T. "Innovative pedagogical Technologies in the English Language Teaching." Tashkent, 2017.
5. [inkedin.com](https://www.linkedin.com)
6. <https://greenhearttravel.org/blog/teach-abroad-programs/teaching-tips-tuesday-how-to-structure-a-basic-esl-lesson-plan>
7. Verbitsky A. A. Competency-based approach and contextual learning theory. - M.: Itspgps, 2004. - 84 p.
8. Zagvyazinsky V. I. Modeling in the structure of socio-pedagogical design // Bulletin of the Higher School. - 2004. - No 9. - S. 21-25.
9. Lavrent'ev G. V., Lavrent'eva N. B., Neodaxina N. A. innovative training technologies for training specialists. Part 2. - Barnaul: Alt. on-ta, 2002. - 185 b.
10. Petukhova T. P. Students ' competence-oriented asynchronous independent work // higher education today. - 2011. - No 6. - B. 6-10.
11. Plotnikova E. B. Pedagogical technologies of education of students in the humanities // science, culture, world of Education. - 2011. - No 3. - B. 108-110.
12. Romanov P. Yu. Educational technology // scientific work of Moscow State Pedagogical University. Series: Natural Sciences. - 2001. - S. 290-294.
13. Saigushev N. Ya. Free management of the educational professional development process: dis. ... Dr ped. Disciplines. - Magnitogorsk, 2002. – 408s